

D5.4 (M48) - Report of recommended implementation strategy for FAIR sharing of human data (an ELIXIR Norway ELIXIR₃ deliverable)

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Report prepared by: [Federico Bianchini](#)

Contributors: [Sveinung Gundersen](#)

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Context

This report provides an update on the work of Task 5.2 of WP5. The scope of this task is to facilitate the creation and sharing of data that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) by aligning with national and international stakeholders. This document is a direct continuation of activities defined in D5.2¹, which also contains a detailed description of the status of the metadata models in use. The present deliverable provides updates on the models and their implementation; however, please refer to D5.2 for a more comprehensive coverage. The final scope of these activities is to enable the deposition of a variety of sensitive omics data in the Norwegian Federated Genome-Phenome Archive (FEGA Norway) using FAIR-enabling metadata models, which will maximise the impact of the data and promote its reuse.

Delivery

The FEGA metadata working group (WG), already introduced in D5.2, keeps on playing a pivotal role in this context. This group comprises a number of metadata experts working in the field of human data, and its scope is to facilitate the creation of a rich and FAIR-oriented metadata solution to be adopted at the European level, a scope very much in line with the activities of the task being reported here. Members of this task actively participate in this group's meetings to help define the model. Since the last report, there have been a couple of notable developments to be mentioned here. Firstly, a workshop concerning the technical usage of ELIXIR biovalidator² was delivered by this group. ELIXIR biovalidator is a

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10708429>

² <https://github.com/elixir-europe/biovalidator>

JSON Schema validator extended from the JavaScript library AJV³. As part of this workshop, members of this task developed hands-on expertise on the usage of this tool. The most important development is the publication of the FEGA Metadata technical report to Zenodo⁴, where a member of this task contributed as a reviewer. The report is extremely detailed and outlines the technical implementation of the model and a number of use cases, including the collection of phenotypic data associated with the main dataset using the Phenopacket standard⁵. The latter is a standard from the Genome Alliance for Genomic and Health (GA₄GH), which is seen as a target format for clinical data, often available in the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) format⁶. Mapping across these standards is, thus, fundamental for increasing the quality⁷ of submissions. This task is also participating in the FAIR FEGA project⁸, an ELIXIR Hub-funded Commissioned Service from ELIXIR's *Human data and translational research* Science Tier. As part of this activity, task members are starting to apply the above considerations to Cancer Data, in collaboration with personnel at the Oslo University Hospital.

Outcomes

The main beneficiaries of this deliverable are:

- Data stewards who are looking for a state-of-the-art technical implementation of metadata models that describe sensitive data.
- Researchers who want to deposit their data in a FAIR-compliant manner.
- Infrastructure providers who want to enable GDPR-compliant deposition and sharing of sensitive data of clinical origin.

The activity described here is a very demanding task that can only be accomplished through synergistic European collaborations. The metadata model has been completed, but it is still not in production, and this certainly represents the next step of such an activity. In ELIXIR Norway, we are also aiming at improving the way we handle metadata, as better tools will facilitate working with complex metadata models such as the new one suggested for FEGA. It is also important to prioritise the mapping between OMOP and Phenopackets (see above), as this is a necessary step for the seamless management of clinical data in a FAIR-compliant way.

³ <https://ajv.js.org/the/>

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18802072>

⁵ <https://www.ga4gh.org/product/phenopackets/>

⁶ <https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization/>

⁷ Note that in this context the word *quality* does not refer to the condition of the data but, rather, to the richness of the metadata and to their compliance with the FAIR principles, including the usage of the proper semantic artifacts

⁸ <https://elixir-europe.org/how-we-work/scientific-programme/science/hdtr/fair-fega>